

Reflexions on MCCT 26 T13

Artistic Practice in the Age of Technology: Fatigue, Failure, and Resistance.

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Summary

Context

This paper reflects on having attended Theme 13 ('T13') of the Midlands Conference In Critical Thought 2026, held at the University of Warwick, UK on May 21st and May 22nd 2026.

Theme 13 is entitled *Artistic Practice in the Age of Technology: Fatigue, Failure, and Resistance*, and coordinated by Abby Brown, Renia Korma, Patrick Loan, and Ziegi Boss, Vienna Contemporary Art Space. For abstracts of all the papers referenced in T13, see the ['Programme'](#).

PractiseSpeak

Figure 1 is a visual summary of the series of papers presented,¹ in order they were given, using a graphic language ('PractiseSpeak') that is introduced below. PractiseSpeak can be used to explore similarities in artistic scenarios that combine humans, tools and machines, including computers and capabilities such as artificial intelligence (AI), including large language models (LLMs).

¹ Numbers in Figure 1 indicate the relevant page numbers where the corresponding presentation is summarised in the Programme.

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Figure 1 - Theme 13. Artistic Practice in the Age of Technology summary

Synthesis

The next major section is a [synthesis](#) across common elements of all the material presented in T13 as follows:-

We distinguish specific aspects of agency in collaboration between humans and automata by:

- Describing the types of [interacting Agents](#);
- Sketching a model to [classify roles](#) of their Agency, building on material presented in some T13 talks.

We develop a formal model - which we call 'Practice Speak', an example of which is shown in Figure 1 - to emphasize types of ways in which Agents can:

- [Relate](#) to one-another and to artifacts and representations that pertain to the scenario;
- [Qualify relationships](#), for example when humans interact with a computer; and
- [Modify conditions](#), such as artifacts being subject to error, agency to a 'glitz', or being fictional.

For fun, we explore by using [emojis](#) as the graphical representation in Practice Speak, and [demonstrate](#) the approach by showing the phrases that correspond to each of the talks.

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Detailed reflexions

The rest of this paper provides detailed comments on each of the talks, grouped by the major themes that arise:-

- Considerations of [mind v. body](#):
 - [Rebalancing creative blocks](#);
 - Considering the importance of [embodying](#); and
 - Illustrating how AI technologies can [expand personas](#) of artists.
- Discussing [Interactions](#) between [human & virtual](#) Agents and with:
 - [Objects](#) (such as artefacts of artistic output);
 - [Representations](#) (such as internal information such as computer programs, or prompts to an LLM); and
 - Creating [uncertainty propagation](#).
- Enumeration of the important [tensions](#):
 - [Machine v. human](#)
 - [Agencies & incentives](#)
 - [Human v. automaton asymmetry](#)
 - [Process v. noise -> emergence](#)
 - [Error v. glitch -> inspiration](#)
 - [Fiction v. non-fictional -> inspiration](#)
 - [Interpretability v. agency](#)
 - [Individual agency v. hivemind](#).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have summarised our reflections having attended most of the talks in Theme 13 of MCCT 26 on Artistic Practice in the Age of Technology: Fatigue, Failure, and Resistance.

Our synthesis has surfaced common elements: firstly, distinguishing specific aspects of agency (human & machine) and classifying the roles of different agents in collaborative scenarios; and culminating in the description of PractiseSpeak. PractiseSpeak is a formalism to represent a unified visual summary of artistic practices illustrated by most of the presentations. It helps to draw our patterns in the diversity and similarity of interactions of humans and automatons in the pursuit of artistic endeavour, and may provide a catalyst to suggest new types of collaboration.

We also discussed in detail major themes that arose in T13, considering balance between mind & body, humans & virtual agency, and highlighting a series of tensions that may arise, many of which can give rise to inspiration.

The author plans to apply PractiseSpeak to his practice, and to extend the approach to a formalism that can also express spatial and temporal dimensions.

Reflexions on MCCT 26 T13

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Synthesis

Interacting Agents

To help unify language of this synthesis, we consider the schema shown in Figure 2, which comprises of:

- *Agents* - autonomous entities - whether human or machines - that may undergo intentional interactions;
- *Objects* - non autonomous entities ('things') in the environment, some of which may be the artistic output of an Agent (an 'artifact'); and
- *Representations* - logical (and therefore virtual) models of some system of Agents and/or Objects, used, for example, to describe a design (e.g. a program).

These entities are assumed to exist in a common *Frame*, which defines their shared context and separates the system from the rest of the world.

Figure 2 - schema of 'things' and their interactions (adapted from source^{2,3})

Each entity of a given type can have relationships with other entities, denoted by the lines in Figure 2. For example, an

² References in this form are to the theme (T13), and page number of the [MCCT 26 Programme](#).

³ Brown. T13, p10.

Agent may produce an Object, using (in part) a Representation; and an Agent may create a Representation (e.g. when writing a program or drafting a design), or view it (e.g. looking at a map or a computer game display).

Classifying Agency

An Agent must have some level of agency, relative to their incentives. However, in general, their level of agency is tempered by those of other Agents, for example, whether members of their community, or constraints resulting from computer systems such as AI services or workflow requirements.

Figure 3 is a schematic that characterises the types of Agents that can participate (i.e. interact) in the context of a game ('Game 1').

Figure 3 - types of Agents in a game (adapted from source⁴)

It is assumed that many users behave normally in Game1 (denoted by the central grey ellipse in the figure). These are distinguished from types of somewhat anomalous Agents, who may adopt these types of role:

⁴ Šimunović, T13, p60.

Synthesis

- *Non-engaged* opt out of the game: for them it has no meaning;
- *Lurkers* just watch, so they do not assimilate the interactive attributes of the game;
- *Hackers* seek to subvert the game, according to some incentive that is typically not aligned with normal users of the game, so are not compliant with its rules; and
- *Hivemind* accumulates data and information, and exercises Agency as an overarching presence (such as the gaming platform) yet it has no identity like other users.

Note that in this context, a 'game' may be considered more generally as a collaboration between a multiplicity of Agents.

[I think it is important to extend this model to consider the types of interactions between games. Figure 4 shows that when two games are considered, two new types of Agent arise:-

- *Aggregators* accumulate data and information across more than one game, and may take actions in one or more games that are not visible to other Agents.
- *Others* are non-engaged in both games, but are potentially active in other games.

Figure 4 - types of Agents in multiple games

Note also that the relationship that a given Agent has in one game may be different in another. For example, a Lurker in Game1 may be watching for information that they may then use as a Hacker in Game2.⁵

Relating agency

We can depict the relationships between Agents using a notation that comprises an alphabet of characters, and strings (i.e. an ordered set of them). Strings are read from left to right.

So, for example, 'A-o' and 'A-r' respectively represent a human Agent (denoted by 'A') producing an Object ('o'), or a Representation (denoted by 'r').

Similarly, an automaton (denoted by 'a') can make an Object directly: 'a-o'. Or it can take input from a Representation (such as a prompt to an LLM) to generate an Object: 'r-a-o'. It may also output a Representation, say when requested to output some code for a computer language: 'r-a-r'.

We use the notation '...' to denote that the string can be attached to the start or end of other strings. For example:

- '...A' denotes that an Agent take input from other strings, and
- 'o...' that the Object may be input to other Agents.

⁵ Items in square brackets '[...]' were not discussed at the conference, but have been added by the Author.

Synthesis

For example, the processes of:

- Viewing an artifact could be shown as: ‘...o-A’, where the provenance of the Object is not explicit in the string; and
- Documenting an act of creative agency could be denoted ‘...A-o’, where the ‘o’ denotes the audit trail artifact, and can in principle be attached to any string where an Agent does something.

There are two distinct cases of using a tool to produce an Object:

- Where the tool has no agency, denoted: ‘...r-A-o’; and
- Where the tool has agency (such as using an AI or program), denoted: ‘a-r-A-o’, or ‘...r-a-r-A-o’.

Here, the tool is denoted by its Representation ‘r’.

Here are examples depicting two types of collaboration:

- ‘A1-r-A2-o’ where agents act in turn (e.g. round-robin); and
- ‘{A1, A2, ...}-r-A-o’, where more than one Agent (A1, A2, etc) co-create a Representation that Agent A uses to create an Object.

The hivemind is similar to this last case, where the final step is done by an automaton: ‘{A1, A2, ...}-r-a-r...’.

One form of collaboration is asymmetric sharing, where, say, an automaton accumulates Objects from other Agents, e.g. : {A1-o1, A2-o2, ...}-a-O...’, where ‘O’ denotes a much larger, aggregated Object than ‘o1’ and ‘o2’. This scenario is common on the Internet, and of fundamental importance to AI Agents.

Qualifying relationships

The internal interactions between [mind and body](#) are important for [rebalancing creative blocks](#) and [embodying](#) maker actions to increase agency and capacity; while realisation of [artistic personas](#) can be expanded into the virtual realm.

[Human Agent - Object](#) and [-Representation](#) interactions wholly in the physical realm appear to be important; although new forms of [human - virtual Agent](#) interactions are giving humans more agency than, say, traditional video games.

Such relationships can be further qualified as follows:

- ‘=’ denotes an embodied relationship;
- ‘- -’ denotes a relationship using a graphical user interface (GUI), such as when a human Agent uses a computer to interact with an automaton.

A relationship can also be qualified further to denote an iteration:

‘~’, ‘≅’; and ‘~ ~’ for a looping simple, embodied and GUI relationship.

For example,

- ‘r≅A-o’ denotes a human Agent making an Object by drawing upon an internal representation (thought, notion, instinct, etc) from their own mind in a reflexive relationship; and
- ‘{A1, A2, ...}-r-a-o’, where a hivemind makes an Object using inputs from multiple human Agents.

Uncertainty seems to be important to art making: for example, see [creating with uncertainty propagation](#), and by seeking [value from uncertainty](#).

Synthesis

Our notation also enables the succinct visualisation of the source of a series of tensions that can arise, each of which needs to be actively balanced.

[Machine v. human](#), and especially [agencies & incentives](#) of various human and automatic Agents, taking account of current [asymmetries](#) between the different types.

Hence, the notation distinguishes human (A) and machine (a) Agents, and can distinguish interactions through a screen (e.g. viewing a program on a computer ‘a-r’). The use of capital and miniscule fonts (e.g. ‘O’ and ‘o’) can be used to show asymmetry.

Modifying conditions

The juxtaposition of [determinate process v. noise](#) can give rise to emergence that benefits artistic endeavour, and [errors & glitches](#) can also give rise to inspiration.

Similarly, the contrasts between [fiction v. non-fictional](#) can give rise to inspiration.

To support these observations, in Table 1 we define two types of modifier that can apply to Agents, Objects, and Representations.

Table 1 - types of modifiers

Entity type	Modifier type	
	Error or glitz	Fictional
Agent	‘Ā’, or ‘â’	‘Ā’, ‘ā’
Object	‘Ô’, ‘ô’	‘Ō’, ‘ō’
Representation	‘Ř’, ‘ř’	‘Ŕ’, ‘ř’

[Note that we do not seek specifically to indicate ‘truth’ due to the breadth of this concept especially in view of the

fundamentally different ways in which human and automatic Agents manipulate ‘truth’. For example, a human may deploy rational thought, predicated on logic, whereas a LLM does not recognise rational truths, but rather uses probability distributions to prioritise its outputs.]

[It is possible for a relationship to introduce an error also, but this is not considered here.]

Depicting tensions

To be used legitimately in a string, a Representation (‘r’) must be interpretable by both its creator and any reader.

However there is often a tension between [interpretability v. agency](#), which can be surfaced by whether or not the ‘r’ symbol is used in a string. For example, when a person reads text in a document in a language that they understand, the string may be ‘...o-r-A’, while if they do not understand the language (or the text is gibberish), it would reasonably be written ‘...o-A’.

Note however that even though the interpretation may be possible in principle, there may be errors in translation, depicted: ‘...o-ř-A’.

Notice that the tension between [individual agency v. hivemind](#) can be visualised by the string ‘{A1, A2, ...}-r-a-o’, where multiple human Agents collaborate, or compete through their GUIs with Representation of an automaton, ultimately resulting in an Object. This is a simple way of depicting a multi-user computer game.

Synthesis

Emoji

It is possible to depict strings using different alphabets of symbols that have equivalent significance to those described above using Latin characters. For example:

- Emojis that use symbols whose meanings are somewhat instinctual; and
- Graphics that are more in the style of a flow diagram (say).

Table 2 shows suggestions of a rendering using emojis.

Table 2 - emoji rendering

<i>Symbol</i>	<i>Emoji</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
A, a		Human, automatic Agent
Â, â		Error-prone Agent
O, o		Object, such as an artifact from artistic practice
Ô, ô		Error-prone Object
R, r		Representation
Î, î		Error-prone Representation
-		Relationship (unqualified)
~		Looping relationship
- -		Relationship with a machine, using its GUI

Synthesis

Demonstrating the approach

Table 3 shows the textual and emoji strings in the PractiseSpeak formalism that represent scenarios described in many of the talks given in the Theme 13. The examples are shown with roughly increasing complexity down the table.

Table 3 - PractiseSpeak textual and emoji renderings of scenarios in T13

Scenario	Textual string	Emoji string	Comments
Direct art-making	A-o	😊▶🖼️	E.g. <i>pan wan</i> ⁶
Virtual influencers ⁷	a-{o, ...}	⚙️▶{🖼️, ...}	Emulating human influencers
Embodying hand tools	r-A-o	📊=😊▶🖼️	E.g. woodworking ⁸
	r-A-r-o	📊=😊▶📊▶🖼️	E.g. blockprinting ⁹
Guided experience ¹⁰	A'-r={A, ...}-o	😊'▶📊= {😊, ...}▶🖼️	
Schram 2.0 meta-art ¹¹	{A, ...}~ ~ r-â-{o, ...}	{😊, ...}🌀🌀📊🌀{🖼️, ...}	Meta-art using AI ...
	a1-{o, ...}	⚙️▶{🖼️, ...}	'a1' acts as a virtual persona.
Inspired by glitches ¹²	a-ô{, ...}- -A-o	⚙️▶{🔥, ...} ▶▶😊▶🖼️	
Feed video game ¹³	...a~{o, ...} -- {A, ...}~a...'	...⚙️🌀{🖼️, ...} ▶▶ {😊, ...}🌀⚙️...	'... // ...' indicates a continuous loop

⁶ Luan et al. T3, p11.

⁷ Sun. T13, p 17.

⁸ Good. T13, p52-53.

⁹ Nicolaou. T13, p33-34.

¹⁰ Stenton. T13, p68-69.

¹¹ Schrem. T13, p61.

¹² Quinn. T13, p24.

¹³ Huh. T13, p16.

Synthesis

Readers misinterpretate ... ¹⁴	A-r-o... ...{ř-A', ...}		... when reading made-up texts.
No answer from the hive ¹⁵	{A, ...}-r-a- {r, ...}.		● indicates '...' is not possible
AI workflows & interpreting processes ¹⁶	A- -r-a-{r, ...} - -A~r...		Doing what it says.
	...r- -A~ ~ a-{r, ...}...		Understanding becomes a loop
Machine drawing & emergence ¹⁷	{A- -r-a; A} -ř-o		A human Agent acts directly in parallel with a programmed machine.
Disrupted drawing ¹⁸	{A, ...; A', ...}~ {ř, ...}-{A, ...}-o		A' indicates disruptive Agents.

Representing space & time

While the PractiseSpeak notation does provide a modifier to indicate embodiment, it does not provide a way of showing spatial-temporal relationship between Agents, and their Objects and Representations. We plan to generalise the model to support these relationships, and to unify this approach with other work the author is doing to represent and analyse new societies in the pervasive presence of automata.

This approach considers a language of virtue to interface better with automata; as well as coping with complexity at scale by using a mathematically formal representation.

Specifically, the biGraph formalism, developed by Cambridge mathematician Robin Milner,¹⁹ provides a mathematically rigorous application of Category Theory to specify a modelling framework for agents.²⁰

¹⁴ Ao, T13, p67-68.

¹⁵ Lin. T13, p16.

¹⁶ Boss, T13, p53.

¹⁷ Melchor. T13, p54.

¹⁸ Loan. T13, p 33.

¹⁹ Milner, Robin. (2009). "The Space and Motion of Communicating Agents." Cambridge University Press.

²⁰ See Galwas, P.A. (2026). "The New Society: Introducing a formalism for identity and societal structures in the face of intelligent automata." At MCCT 26, Theme 3, and references therein.

Detailed reflections

Mind v. body

Rebalancing creative blocks

Creative fatigue and moments of artistic blockage may be influenced by digital tools and technology-driven workflows, so that we become:²¹

- “Unable to pass beyond conception to reach a next step”; or
- Locked into a ‘level’ of thinking, or making too many iterations in the same direction.

To combat this we may:

- Reset delivery expectations [e.g. the artifact (Object) perceived as the important output];
- Change the lens onto information, for example to ‘rebalance’ the judgement of the value of information [changing the Frame, Representations, nature of agency or intention, and/or the Frame itself]; and
- Randomly prune information or options [specifically in the interactions with Objects or Representations of them].²²

For example, in physical journeys directed by a satnav [which displays a Representation], the system biases through a lens of efficiency and optimisation. In contrast, *Memory Walks* explores the relationships of an individual with physical space through their imagination and memory alone:²³

“Through slow and purposeful hybrid engagements both on and off screen,

participants will rely on memory and instinct to wander, journey and arrive.”

There is some sense of balancing “creation & boredom”, and there may be fears of “not being busy”, or of needing to “fill up time” with doing.

[This sense may depend on the ratio of design v. making, and perhaps reaching saturation when there is too much designing. Designing could be seen primarily as the interactions of an Agent with a Representation; while ‘making’ is the relationship between an Agent and their artifacts (Objects) that they make.]

Challenging assumptions [which is ultimately an act of the mind] can be seen as a change in the nature of the Representation, or an Agent’s relationship with a Representation; or in extreme cases, a redefinition of the Frame.

For example, the horror commonly arises in weird fiction, such as when plants adopt animality (e.g. *The Day of the Triffid*),²⁴ [likely due to embedded assumptions (or Frames) of the differences between plants and animals].

Embodying

Embodying actions taken by an Agent would appear to be important, whether in creating an Object [i.e. making] or a Representation of one [e.g. designing]:-

“The slow and reflective playfulness of embodied approaches that deliberately break patterns—walking, mindful

²¹ Korma. T13, p34.

²² Korma. T13, p34.

²³ Bhargave. T13, p42.

²⁴ Brown. T3, p10.

Detailed reflections

breathing, tactile practices, somatic improvisation, communal singing and dancing, or repetitive hand-drawings—recenter human experience by resisting the logic that art like routes must be optimised, quantified and quick; they create room for chance, error, meditation and ambiguity. Taking the long way home becomes a site of playful rebellion against automation, technological commands, and passive consumption of digital systems and their Instructions.”²⁵

[Of course, such embodying is typically assumed to apply only to human Agents.

In contrast, we can in principle imagine automata embodying in two different ways: AI systems that ‘learn’ from their input data; and automata that design a Representation that they realise physically (say making with a 3D printer).]

Expanding personas

Agency can be manifested by individual persons, by autonomous machines - such as computers and artificial intelligence (AI) systems - and we are also seeing the combination of the two acting with various degrees of symmetry and alignment of intent.

[Schram 2.0](#) demonstrates a virtual artist whose agency and artifacts [encapsulated in a persona] are mediated by interactions between one or more human individuals and AI capabilities, in a constantly evolving feedback loop between human and machine, which constitutes a form of distributed selfhood.²⁶

“This alter ego embodies an alternative life path where artistic ambition and personal freedom take center stage, unencumbered by caregiving responsibilities, professional and financial restraints. SCHRAM2.0 functions as a meta-artwork that explores the boundaries between reality and fiction, facilitated by collaboration with artificial intelligence.”²⁷

The combination of the feedback loops and the fundamental indeterminacy of the AI system can give rise to emergence, including material inconsistency. Such scenarios pose challenges for current concepts and practices of authorship, sharing and community as an artwork.²⁸

This scenario can be shown in PractiseSpeak as: ‘{A1, ...}~r-â{o1, ...}’ which emulates ‘a1-{o1, ...}’, where ‘a1’ is a virtual persona of ‘A1’.

²⁵ Bhargave. T13, p42.

²⁶ Schrem. T13, p61.

²⁷ <https://www.laurie-schram.nl/schram2-0>

²⁸ Schrem. T13, p61.

Detailed reflections

Interactions

Human Agent - Object

Pan wan - small hand-held objects, such as a pair of walnuts, become imbued with *Bajian* - “patina” - a change to the object making it a “part of us”,²⁹ the human Agent.

Human Agent - Representation

A graphic designer and book designer does letterpress production to “get away” from the screen,³⁰ while an artist is taking his making towards working with wood for similar reasons.³¹

Both are reducing their interaction with Representations, and increasing it with Objects: in PractiseSpeak ‘r-A-r-o’,³² and ‘r-A-o’ respectively.³³

In both cases, the physicality of the Object and process of interaction with it were cited as an important aspect. [However, there may also be an effect due to the change in cognitive interactions for making a physical Object compared with a virtual design Representation.]

Human - virtual Agent

Virtual influencers (VIs) - with dynamic levels of functionality and authenticity - are emerging in the virtual world alongside human influences. Those with human-like representations seem to arouse more suspicion in the humans who interact with them compared with obviously digital characters that do not seek to emulate humans.³⁴

²⁹ Luan et al. T3, p11.

³⁰ Nicolaou. T13, p33-34.

³¹ Good. T13, p52-53.

³² Nicolaou. T13, p33-34.

³³ Good. T13, p52-53.

³⁴ Sun. T13, p 17.

VIs can be depicted: ‘a-{o, ...}’.

Loopntale’s Feed (2022/2025) video game takes a different stance relative to the agency of the automaton, and the nature of the relationship with the humans who interact with it:-

“Feed is a video game that makes perceptible the invisible rhythms of nonhuman agents inhabiting liminal urban spaces.”³⁵

In contrast to traditional video games, Feed has no goals for the human Agent to achieve, and it uses its own autonomous agency to create outputs and archives (virtual Objects). This environment allows the exploration by (human) users, “reclaiming the space for thought”, through “slow assembly”, allowing them to “sit with confusion”³⁶

“The game becomes an experimental space between reality and simulation, in which the player’s actions lead to new ways of relating and shifts in perception. Focusing on the new possibilities of solidarity sparked by the player’s actions, Loopntale creates conditions for imagining connection rather than isolation.”³⁷

Feed can be represented as the eternal loop; “...a~{o, ...}- {A, ...}~a...”.

³⁵

<https://unfoldx.org/en/exhibition/artists/overseas-en/loopntale/>

³⁶ Huh. T13, p16.

³⁷

<https://unfoldx.org/en/exhibition/artists/overseas-en/loopntale/>

Detailed reflections

Creating with uncertainty

The meaningful [Representation] is measurable, yet it is subjected to classification and optimisation to govern, within inherent uncertainty [i.e. statistical confidence limits]. Yet propagated uncertainties may be creatively productive.

This view mirrors considerations of tiny initiating events (TIEs) and their potential for sourcing variety, and scaleably through two primary non-linear types of operations, namely cloning and extraction.³⁸

“The history of ‘propagated uncertainty’ teaches us that acknowledging uncertainty doesn't mean abandoning knowledge—it means characterising knowledge more accurately.”³⁹

“The new art forms emerging from contemporary technologies aren't replacing traditional art but expanding the possibility space; adding new dimensions of uncertainty to explore, new transformation functions to navigate.”⁴⁰

Value from uncertainty

“Rather than demanding impossible certainty or rejecting the new entirely, we can learn what Gauss and Laplace taught: understand your uncertainties, trace how they propagate, and make decisions informed by that understanding rather than pretending certainty you don't have.”⁴¹

Contemporary creative practice needs similar frameworks that help balance

³⁸ Galwas, P.A. (2021). “[Classifying Complex Dynamics of Commercial Ecosystems.](#)”

Zenodo.

³⁹ Cloke. T13, p42.

⁴⁰ Cloke. T13, p42.

⁴¹ Cloke. T13, p42.

freedom v. vulnerability. “We can acknowledge that:

- Authorship in collaborative human-AI systems is distributed and uncertain;
- Originality [often?] involves novel configurations of influences, not creation from nothing;
- Cultural value emerges from complex interactions between scarcity, meaning, context, and community [and ethics];
- Identity in digital spaces is performative, multiple, and irreducibly uncertain.

They [i.e. these practices] fit within our cultural landscape ... by challenging us to develop richer frameworks for thinking about creativity, value, and meaning in systems where uncertainty propagates in increasingly visible and undeniable ways.”⁴²

[Such frameworks must cope with the massive scale and speed of autonomous Agents, relative to human Agents; as well as the need to address imprecisions and cascading impacts of important qualities that cannot easily be rendered into numerical metrics, such as human values.⁴³]

[Distributed emergent systems make the attribution of responsibility logically impossible. For example, see Floridi on distributed moral responsibility (DMR),⁴⁴

⁴² Cloke. T13, p42.

⁴³ E.g. see Galwas, T3, p69.

⁴⁴ Floridi, L. (2016). “Faultless responsibility: on the nature and allocation of moral responsibility for distributed moral actions. “Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A 20160112. Available from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2016.0112>.

Detailed reflections

and Galwas (2026)⁴⁵ on DMR and causal inference in agentic AI systems.

This argument makes ascribing a seat for intellectual property challenging, and likely renders the concept of *de minimis* unfounded.]

Tensions

Machine v. human

Using art as a “catalyst for discussion” in the age of technology, these pieces explore information overload, surveillance: privacy, and sentiment analysis, e.g.:

- “Serious about play”
- Absurdity and laughing
- Documenting experiences.⁴⁶

[Specifically, each piece of art is an Object that seeks to demonstrate aspects of human-machine interactions, often exposing absurdity and invoking humour.]

Agencies & incentives

“By framing use itself as the subject of the artwork, ... my work operates by taking technological promises literally and inhabiting their prescribed workflows over extended durations, ... reveal[ing] the warping, performance, and absurdity that occurs when systems are followed correctly.”⁴⁷

An example of this scenario is:

‘A- -r-a-{r, ...}- -A~r... ‘.

“[S]ystems promise efficiency, insight, or elevation, yet deliver meta-work,

performance, and the colonization of consciousness when fully implemented,” They embed internal contradictions in a process.⁴⁸

Moreover, transparency causes opacity: “metawork that gets nothing done”, so documentation increases, e.g. in the corporate context and in the face of compliance requirements, yet comprehension reduces.”⁴⁹

This can be depicted by the eternal loop: ‘...r- -A~r... ‘.

[In a sense these scenarios demonstrate competition between different types of Agency: the automaton, through its system of workflow, is impacting the agency of the human user, especially when the incentives of the two Agents do not align.]

“Designed within capitalist incentive structures that prioritize scalability, self-perpetuation, and measurable performance, these systems continue to function even as their outputs become increasingly abstracted from lived experience. ... The issue is not malfunction but success: these systems work as designed, and it is precisely through their correct operation that their absurdities become visible.”⁵⁰

[Hence, the outputs of work (Objects) become conflated with the Representation used to support transparency of working (e.g. compliance logs), and multiple layers of documents are typically required to understand and support the Representation.]

⁴⁵ Galwas, P. A. (2026, March 12). “[Challenge: Causal inference, agentic AI and distributed moral responsibility.](#)” Zenodo.

⁴⁶ Good. T13, p52-53.

⁴⁷ Boss, T13, p53.

⁴⁸ Boss, T13, p53.

⁴⁹ Boss, T13, p53.

⁵⁰ Boss, T13, p53.

Detailed reflections

[See, for example, a classification of types of work in the context of the team:

Belbin, R. Meredith. (2000). "[Beyond the Team](#)." Routledge.

For example 'Pink work' can be discovered by answers to the question "Did you have to spend time on anything that did not contribute to your work objectives?" It includes:

- Collection of redundant information;
- Requests for information that is never used;
- Continuing to collect information that is no longer cost-effective or relevant; and
- Unplanned waiting time (Why are we waiting?).⁵¹

Human v. automaton asymmetry

"In contemporary socio-technical systems, visibility has become a scarce and quota-based privilege rather than an inherent right. Platforms, welfare agencies, and algorithmic scoring systems increasingly shape who appears in public, whose narratives are amplified, and whose presence is filtered out. ... [V]isibility today operates as a designed and distributed resource."⁵²

Relationships between human and automatic Agents have become asymmetric. There is a "silence unworthy of explanation", where inputs are not acknowledged and rejection is not qualified by automata.⁵³

The consequences of this are typically not predictable by those who interact with such systems, so they cannot know how to

'play the game' and they face their wider visibility effectively being denied.

This can be depicted in PractiseSpeak as:

{A, ...}-r-a-{r, ...}' ,

where the full stop indicates that no continuations are permitted.⁵⁴

Process v. noise -> emergence

Combining the unpredictable - in a spirit of "serious play"⁵⁵ - with the predictable (say of a process or program), is demonstrated by "draw with noise", for example where human input generates emergence in an artifact being drawn by a pen-plotter.

This approach can be depicted:

{A- r-a; A}-ř-o.

The source of emergence can be seen as arising from the combination of the dynamics of two loops, which constitute a complex adaptive system (CAS):

- Dialog between the human Agent and the developing artifact, e.g. based on visual feedback; and
- Dynamic processes that impact the mark-making, e.g. by adding a liquid to mix with the plotter ink on the surface of the paper.

Error v. glitch -> inspiration

In her "[Glitch Studies Manifesto](#)" (2011), Rosa Menkman argues that glitches are not merely errors but moments that "break the flow of the ordinary" and expose the normally invisible structures of systems. Glitches create "a lost opportunity to make the machine conform to protocol" and thus represent moments of deviation, rupture, and possibility.

⁵¹ (Belbin 2000) Chapter 5. See [here](#).

⁵² Lin. T13, p16.

⁵³ Lin. T13, p16.

⁵⁴ Lin. T13, p16.

⁵⁵ Melchor. T13, p54.

Detailed reflections

[Glitches, Blips and Bugs](#) VCAS June 2025 explores interplay of creative methods in the face of interruption. In the T13 Q_plus_I workshop, drawers attempt to reproduce an image, while following instructions, yet their actions are restricted by interrupters, for example by having parts of their body taped up.⁵⁶

This can be shown as:

{A, ...; A', ...}~{A, ...}-o'

In another case, "error making defines life", motivated art created from glitches in satellite photographs of ice sheets breaking down in Antarctica.⁵⁷

This scenario can be depicted as:

'...a-{o, ...}-A-o'.

"More critically, I examine whether these moments of failure constitute the last point for human presence within environmental observation - spaces where subjective meaning reasserts itself against total operational images, or whether even our errors have become predictable, algorithmic, and automated."⁵⁸

Fiction v. non-fictional -> inspiration

The tension between fiction and non-fiction has inspired a series of themes for artistic exploration. For example, money became a "false promise" after the suspension of the Gold Standard, inspiring the Schram coin, and silver dollar.⁵⁹

And, in the virtual realm, exploration of:

- Virtual brand Schram & Sandher lifestyle brand;
- S&S Jewellery - predicated on rule-based generation that uses "rationality to oppress logic"; and
- Edible currencies as a mitigation for inflation.⁶⁰

Interpretability v. agency

[Xu Bing](#) explored the relationship between interpretation and the agency of readers of the written word:⁶¹

- Books composed of pseudo Chinese characters challenge the reader into unstable interpretations;
- Mapping Latin characters and English words into pseudo Chinese characters proved to be unstable for readers, even though the mapping is fixed, transparent and in principle readable;
- Emoji-based texts can be universally understood but lead to reader fatigue from the accumulation of signs.

This scenario can be shown as:

'A-r-o... ...{f-A', ...}'

[Ponder the number of characters in ancient Egyptian, and the number of Sanskrit root words, compared with the set of emojis.]

[Ponder emoji symbols are the bases of programs that could run on a Universal Turing Machine (UTM). Note that Sanskrit root words are noun verb duals, so can be for the basis for computation (and the

⁵⁶ Loan. T13, p 33.

⁵⁷ Quinn. T13, p24.

⁵⁸ Quinn. T13, p24.

⁵⁹ Schrem. T13, p61.

⁶⁰ Schrem. T13, p61.

⁶¹ Ao, T13, p67-68.

Detailed reflections

grammar is in fact an executable program, written in Sanskrit.])

Individual agency v. hivemind

Each individual's agency [whether human or machine] competes with that of the aggregating hivemind, e.g. see:⁶²

- "Space for collective mind" Barlow, John Perry. (1996). [A Declaration of the Independence of Cyberspace.](#)
- "Control without centre" (Shaviro (2003))
- "Power and control everywhere" Galloway, Alexander R.; Thacker, Eugene. (2007). "[The Exploit: A Theory of Networks.](#)" University of Minnesota Press.

Two forms of agency appear to escape the hivemind (referring to Figure 3&4):⁶³

- Hackers explore and exploit new epistemic territory (Konior 2020); and
- The non-engaged exhibit "total refusal" (Beghetto 2022), Wark (2007, 2004).

[However, as Figure 4 shows, a more complex situation arises when considering multiple, distinct hiveminds (which may interact with each other opaquely), and (say) lurkers in one system that use their intelligence to become hackers in another.]

⁶² Šimunović, T13, p60.

⁶³ Šimunović, T13, p60.